

THE ROLE OF ALISHER NAVOI'S LITERARY WORKS IN YOUTH UPBRINGING

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Annotation: In this article, the scientific heritage of Alisher Navoi and his works are studied and analyzed, and also the educational views of the scientist are described from the point of view of pedagogy.

Key words: pedagogy, educational views, national heritage

INTRODUCTION

Today, relations based on new democratic traditions and principles are being formed. It should be noted that one of the main features of socio-political reforms is their focus on human interests, well-being and perfection.

In this regard, several conditions have been created for studying spirituality, national values, national history and the heritage of our great people in new modern ways.

In particular, recently, the attention of the President to national values, to the study of the heritage of the great people of our country has increased and has given impetus to the further development of work in this regard.

In particular, it was necessary to study the creativity of the great thinker, state and public figure, Sultan Amir Temur and Nizamiddin Alisher Navoi.

Alisher Navoi's spiritual heritage, in particular, his educational views created the possibility of a new, objective, scientific analysis from the point of view of the science of pedagogy, and at the same time made it a necessity. Socio-philosophical, literary and philological issues of Navoi's work have been studied by many scientists. However, the views of the scientist about the perfect person in the field of pedagogy have not been sufficiently studied from a scientific point of view.

Although the views of the scientist about the ideal permeated all the works he wrote during his life, in the images we meet a real, literally perfect man and the heroes of the work "Khamsa".

Alisher Navoi's life was social and it was organized and conducted on the basis of Shariat. That is why religion and shariat issues occupy the main place in Navoi's work. According to the traditions of that time, Navoi's work began with praises to Allah, blessings and prayers of the

Prophet.

"Khayrat-ul Abror" is the first "Khamsa" epic written by Navoi, and he wrote this work when he was 42 years old. So, the experiences and life lessons of a person before adulthood are considered the main theme of this work. In all the stories in the work, there are many assumptions about humanity, the ideal man in the scientist's imagination and his duty to humanity.

Exemplary stories increase impact and appeal. Many of these stories have spread among our people and have already become public property. "Hotami wedding stories", "Nushiravon's garden of modesty...", "Two Loyal Lands", "Poetry and Durroj", "Ayubi Khalaf and Pain", "From Bahram's May Drunkenness..." , the theme "Ul kul karyatikim, ayagi talib..." has not lost its importance even today. The exemplary life of Nushiravon, who is famous for his humility and especially his patience, is also narrated with great magnificence.

Nushiravon falls in love with a beautiful woman in his youth. He works hard to achieve this beauty. Finally, one day he meets his love in a flower garden, he goes to her and talks to her, and when he hugs her, his eyes suddenly fall on a saffron flower. Nargis saw the prince looking at Nushiravon with shy eyes, and after regaining consciousness, she asked him, "Why are you in such a state?" asked Nargiz. The gentle prince, on the contrary, answered: "What hinders me is the autumn of the goldsmith of this age."

Navoi draws the following conclusion from this incident:

- In this work, the nobility in Khayo's eyes gave him strength. His narcissus eyes filled with tears, he stood up and surrendered.

CONCLUSION

Above, we tried to show how valuable the work of the poet is in bringing up a perfect generation. It should be said that the study of Alisher Navoi's work is not enough in general education schools today.

The set goal cannot be achieved with the help of pieces of work given in grades 7 and above. In order to raise a perfect generation, as we said above, it would be appropriate to interpret the stories that stand at the highest place in Navoi's work.

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